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Development Priorities and Current Problems of the Agricultural Sector in the Karabakh and Eastern Zangazur Economic Regions of Azerbaijan

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Abstract: The article examines the priorities and current problems of the development of the agrarian sector in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions of Azerbaijan. The strategic role of the agrarian sector in the country's economy is considered and justified. The priorities for expanding the activities of the agrarian sector in the newly created Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions in the liberated territories are determined. The development prospects and problems of the agrarian sector, which is a traditional sector of the economy, in the modern era are considered in a comprehensive manner. The issues of more efficient organization of the directions of activity of the agrarian sector based on high technologies are analyzed and evaluated. Recommendations are prepared and proposals are made for the intensification of the development of the agrarian sector in Karabakh and East Zangezur in the near and long term.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Karabakh, East Zangezur, economic region, agrarian sector, development priorities of the agrarian sector, current problems of the agrarian sector.

Introduction

World experience shows that one of the main processes observed in post-conflict areas is the mobilization and re-prioritization of budget resources. In the current conditions, the use of this model in Azerbaijan will be more appropriate, and the reconstruction and reconstruction work carried out in these areas is a clear example of this. Referring to the experience of post-conflict countries, we can say that in order to ensure macroeconomic stability, a new economic development strategy must meet certain requirements: phased and consistent implementation of economic reforms; selection of priority private investments; restructuring of monetary and fiscal policy that ensures the recovery of the economy; ensuring fiscal sustainability as the main goal of the implementation of fiscal policy, along with ensuring financing of recovery and employment; restoration of all types of social services for individuals and households; creation of a transparent environment and ensuring efficiency in the management of international aid and various grants; proper establishment of a donor coordination center; formation of institutions that ensure the implementation of the strategy. It should be noted that after World War II, the recovery of the economy in France and Italy, which were post-conflict areas, was based on the Marshall Plan. These states have pursued successful reconstruction policies in the post-conflict period by increasing funding for their countries' priority sectors (Гасымлы, В., 2022).

In modern conditions, strengthening the comprehensive use of the natural resources, productive forces, and overall development potential of Azerbaijan's post-conflict territories is one of the main tasks (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2018). After regaining its independence, Azerbaijan has ensured and made efforts to implement targeted reforms in many areas. For an independent state, the development of various sectors of agriculture, primarily the production areas of important food products, and a comprehensive approach to the agricultural sector in general are important issues. However, in the early 1990s, Armenian armed forces, relying on their foreign patrons, occupied 20% of our lands with the help of heavy weapons, including tanks, left over from the former Soviet empire, and committed massacres and genocides. In the following years, our occupied lands were degraded, our fertile lands turned into gray saline soil, our underground and surface resources were plundered, in short, these areas became useless and, according to various expert estimates, our country suffered about 819 billion dollars in damage (İşğal nəticəsində Azərbaycanla dəymiş ziyan açıqlandı - 818 milyard 880 milyon dollar, 2022).

But in the following years, our economically developing country, our politically influential state in the world, strengthened its army building and at the same time increased the prestige of our country in the international community, and carried out historic work to liberate our lands from occupation. As a result, the Great Karabakh Victory, which began on September 27, 2020 and lasted for 44 days, took place, and our lands were cleared of the enemy. Immediately after this historic victory, large-scale construction and improvement works began. Large-scale work is already being carried out in these directions, on the one hand, a social infrastructure network is being created, on the other hand, conceptual approaches are being determined for the organization of production infrastructure, the reshaping and development of the potential of traditional economic sectors for

the region. In fact, the head of state has repeatedly visited the territories liberated from occupation, participated in various groundbreaking ceremonies, personally participated in the opening of facilities put into operation, and during his public speeches, conceptual approaches have been determined for the revival and development of these territories.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The main purpose of the study is to investigate the development priorities of the agricultural sector in the newly created Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions in the post-conflict area, to clarify current problems and to prepare appropriate action mechanisms. In this regard, a group of tasks will be given more attention, including the resource potential of the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions, the development opportunities of the agricultural sector and priority areas of activity. Substantiation of the effectiveness of the development of the agricultural sector based on "smart" technologies can also be considered one of the main research tasks.

Research Results

In modern times, Azerbaijan has set itself a strategic task to mobilize its potential more quickly by conducting an inventory of these territories. Thanks to the liberation of the occupied territories from the enemy, the country's economy will not only strengthen its power, but also further increase its competitiveness, high-tech agro-industrial sectors will be created, sustainable sources of economic growth will be formed, and all this will ultimately increase national income. The reconstruction and development of post-conflict territories can make an additional contribution to the country's economy. Foreign investment is also needed, but first of all, our country should pay special attention to its own economic strength and financial potential. The effective restoration of these territories will create additional resources for expanding the country's economy (Əliyev Ş.T., 2021). Currently, large-scale measures are being implemented in the post-conflict territories of Azerbaijan to restore all potential and restore post-conflict territories. These territories are very rich and productive in terms of natural resources, flora and fauna. There are 168 valuable ore deposits and 260 thousand hectares of forests in these territories, which means a total area of 1.3 million hectares. Despite the fact that many regions of the world are facing the problem of water resource shortages, 9 reservoirs and 13 large rivers located in the Karabakh territory are of great importance for Azerbaijan and expand the water resources and the entire economic potential of the republic. As for the work carried out in various directions of the reconstruction of post-conflict territories, the clearance of territories from mines for the purpose of carrying out restoration and reconstruction works is an urgent and serious issue. Because for 30 years, Armenian vandals have polluted these lands with military ammunition and mines, making them unsuitable for living and use. Therefore, first of all, a very important issue is to ensure security. Then, the formation of an institutional base, which includes the creation and reconstruction of state administrative structures (Aliyev, Sh.T., 2014). It is well known to everyone that in the territory liberated from occupation there were numerous state structures, organizations, cultural monuments, buildings, and about 900 settlements, the condition of which needs to be seriously inventoried in the modern era. During the occupation, almost all infrastructure in that area was completely destroyed. Therefore, in order to carry out restoration and

reconstruction works, serious work must first be done in the direction of infrastructure construction. Also, it is very important to provide financial support for the work carried out (Musayev, A.F., 2021).

It is known that the goals of “Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities of Socio-Economic Development” are being realized in our country. These processes will increase our country’s chances of becoming a powerful state and will be able to significantly strengthen its national security, as well as our economic security. Thus, the restoration and development of the Karabakh and East Zangezur regions can also be positively assessed from this perspective. Based on the real situation in the post-conflict period, Azerbaijan has set itself the goal of ensuring the revival and development of these economic regions in the near future. In order to accelerate this complex task, proposals reflecting more sound scientific-economic approaches and practical mechanisms should be developed in the agricultural sector, and it may be effective to focus on the following: the creation of agro-industrial parks based on the high agricultural potential of the post-conflict territories, meeting local needs and producing export-oriented products (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2022); Providing quality agrotechnical services for the efficient use of various lands and increasing their productivity; developing crop and livestock farming; efficiently organizing transport and logistics infrastructures and constantly improving their performance to deliver agricultural products to consumers in a timely and high-quality manner in post-conflict areas; reducing measures to reduce risks in the agricultural sector and thus increasing the investment attractiveness of that sector as a source of financing, etc. All of these can also be viewed as important determinants of the country's development (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2010). On the other hand, the formation of more efficient financial sources is important in terms of macroeconomic and macrofinancial stability in the country (Алиев Ш.Т., 2009). In order to improve the structure of the country's foreign trade turnover, in particular, to increase export potential and create import-substituting sectors, the need for the development of the agricultural sector and its main component, the agro-industrial complex, has increased (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2015).

It should be noted that in post-conflict areas, it is necessary to reorganize various agrotechnical services, including land reclamation and water management. For this, the main tasks are to identify lands in need of reclamation, reorganize reservoirs and facilities, prevent water loss, establish water supply facilities to meet the needs of the territories for irrigation water and the population for drinking water, and apply advanced technologies in irrigation in accordance with modern requirements. The main conditions should be the organization of leasing services in Karabakh and East Zangezur, the provision of agricultural machinery and equipment on a leasing basis to individuals and legal entities on preferential terms, and the creation of an agricultural services network. In addition, activities should be carried out to modernize agricultural producers in terms of technical base and management, as a necessary condition for the sustainable development of agriculture and rural areas. The use of modern technological processes in the agricultural sector will contribute to the development of inter-sectoral relations for both small and large farms to be created in these areas, and the formation of cooperative structures (İbrahimov İ.H., 2021). In order to launch farms in post-conflict areas in a short period of time and ensure their smooth operation, it is necessary to form transport and logistics infrastructure. Logistics infrastructure should include

transportation and storage of produced products, as well as ensuring the entry and exit of vehicles and repair of roads. Also, taking into account the resource potential of post-conflict areas, the establishment of reception points for various agricultural products here also plays an important role in terms of transport and logistics infrastructure (Fikrətzadə, F.F., Hacıyeva, S.İ., 2020). Since the competitiveness of post-conflict areas determines their security and development opportunities, improving transport and logistics infrastructure should be a key task that allows creating favorable conditions for improving the lives of the population of these areas. In particular, in such conditions, the application of new economic mechanisms comes to the fore (Алиев Ш.Т., 2009).

It is known that the application of innovations in the agricultural sector is one of the areas requiring high investment. Sustainable development of the agricultural sector in post-conflict areas is possible precisely through the application of innovative technology. In this regard, it is possible to increase the application of innovative technology in the context of agricultural products. It is advisable to stimulate the strengthening of the application of innovations in the agricultural sector of post-conflict areas. It is also necessary to create a single space for the state, researchers and the private sector to conduct research in order to develop the agricultural sector in those areas. Innovation parks can be such a space for the economic development of the agricultural sector (Fikrətzadə, F.F., Babayeva, V.M., 2022). There is a fairly close relationship between uncertainty and risk factors in the agricultural sector. On the other hand, innovative development in the agricultural sector requires risky activities. For this reason, banks are reluctant to invest in innovative development projects here. Studies indeed show that banks often refuse to finance innovative projects due to high uncertainty and relatively low profitability (İbrahimov, M.F., 2022). These or other factors discourage banks from lending to post-conflict areas. Therefore, it is necessary to reduce all types of risks in these areas.

Rehabilitation and reconstruction projects implemented in post-conflict areas include such stages as solving economic recovery problems, ensuring flexible management and security, organizing social services, building modern infrastructure, etc. In the process of reconstruction of post-conflict areas, attention should be paid to a number of important points. In particular, it is important to achieve high population density, adapt infrastructure provision to the sustainable logistics capabilities of these areas, ensure the sustainability of economic development, optimize the volume of required funds, attract private, as well as local and foreign investments to the reconstruction process, and thus stimulate the growth of the country's economy. A significant part of post-conflict areas is made up of mountain forest zones and areas suitable for pastures. These create serious opportunities for the production of meat and dairy products. Especially in the coming years, we can observe the formation of livestock enterprises in post-conflict areas, which also requires some time. Because, the complete clearance of these areas from mines and the elimination of the risks associated with this are among the priority issues. Most likely, in the coming years, Azerbaijan will be able to meet its demand for meat and dairy products at the expense of the livestock farms already formed there. These factors, in turn, will allow improving the structure of the country's economy. At the same time, special attention should be paid to the implementation of the green economy and digital mechanisms. Post-conflict areas are generally in the spotlight as green energy zones (Aliyev, S.,

Gulaliyev, M., Purhani, S., Mehdiyeva, G., & Mustafayev, E., 2024). In such circumstances, wider application of digital and, as we mentioned earlier, "smart" technologies is required (Mamedov, Z.F., Aliyev, Sh.T., Jafarova, N.A., 2020).

The prospects for increasing the efficiency of resource potential use are associated with the constant innovative development of the industry, increasing the competitiveness of products, and increasing the profitability of a resource unit. For this, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of the use of certain types of resources by applying the achievements of the ETT and improving production processes. It is necessary to achieve such a balance of resource potential that would allow obtaining maximum yields. A long-term perspective direction for increasing efficiency is the expansion of product sales, including exports. In general, currently, due to the constant growth of the world population, the demand for products of the agro-food complex is increasing, which requires a multiple increase in production (Потапов, А.П., 2021). The restoration and development of the agricultural potential is one of the main directions of the economic policy implemented in the modern era. The presence of new technologies, modern equipment, financial resources, and an effective mechanism of state regulation can significantly accelerate the process of reforms in the country's agrarian sector. In this context, the goal of the strategy for the development of agricultural enterprises is to accelerate the growth rate of agricultural products by increasing the efficient use of resource potential and the competitiveness of products, and to solve the social problems of rural areas (Давыдкина, О.А., 2013).

Currently, reconstruction and modernization work should be carried out here for the full restoration of these areas. Modernization of the agrarian sector in post-conflict areas should be directed on a systematic basis, based on innovation, to increase the competitiveness of the industry, export potential, and the development of the infrastructure of the agricultural industry. We believe that in the context of the development of a knowledge-based economy, modernization of the agrarian sector necessitates the development of innovations and business incubators through a group of means: development and global integration of a network of centers for the transfer of agricultural innovations; creation and development of venture funds in the agricultural sector; formation of a state mechanism for the creation and development of agricultural innovation clusters; support for agricultural innovations and the creation of a unified innovation system, etc. (Гусейнова, С.Г., 2019).

It should be noted that the development of the agricultural sector in our country is of a principled and strategic nature. In terms of solving the problems of strengthening food security at the global level, the complex and systematic development of the agricultural sector is of great importance (Quliyev, E.A., 2020). In recent times, structural changes and measures to improve management mechanisms in the agrarian sector in our country have attracted attention. In order to develop the agrarian sector in Azerbaijan in line with modern global challenges, it is first of all necessary to adapt its structure to progressive world practice and identify ways to solve efficiency problems (Ataşov, B.X., 2017). These issues are also of a fundamental nature in the liberated territories, and in view of the above factors, the management mechanisms of the agrarian sector in post-conflict areas are based on modern high technologies. The use of more digital and "smart" technologies has been

conceptually determined. A new economic zoning division has already been carried out in Azerbaijan, and by the Decree of the President of the country dated July 7, 2021, two new economic regions were established in the liberated territories - Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions (Azərbaycan Respublikasında iqtisadi rayonların yeni bölgüsü haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Fərmanı, 2021). As a result of such a conceptual approach, it becomes possible to plan the socio-economic development of the regions located in these areas, prepare master plans for cities that are regional centers in a more organized and efficient manner, take economic development measures, and shape the structure of the economy (Əliyev, Ş.T., 2021). The new division of economic regionalization will play a positive role in determining conceptual approaches to the revitalization of the liberated territories and in the objective assessment and efficient use of the resources of each economic region (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2022).

The East Zangezur economic region includes the districts of Jabrayil, Zangilan, Gubadli, Lachin and Kalbajar. Most of these districts have the potential for growing agricultural products and establishing agro-processing enterprises. The creation of the "Araz Valley Economic Zone" has already begun in the Jabrayil district (İlham Əliyev Şərqi Zəngəzur iqtisadi rayonunda "Araz Vadisi İqtisadi Zonası" Sənaye Parkının təməlini qoyub, 2021). Already, measures are being taken to create the appropriate infrastructure in this economic zone, and there are applications from various companies to register as residents in this zone. All of this will accelerate the transition of the socio-economic development processes of the East Zangezur and Karabakh economic regions to the most intensive phase. Despite the formation of new and promising sectors in the structure of the economy of these economic regions, the creation of a powerful transport and logistics system, and the priority of organizing high-tech processing enterprises, in our opinion, the development of traditional economic sectors in these areas will remain a priority, and we would like to especially note the role and importance of the agricultural sector in this direction. All this makes an additional contribution to strengthening the economic security of the country (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2020). At the same time, high technologies allow for the expansion of the provision of economic activity based on (Alguliyev, R.M., Aliyev A.G., Aliyev Sh.T., Shahverdiyeva R.O., 2014). As a result, opportunities for accelerating innovative development are being formed in the country and the structure of an innovation-oriented economy is being created (Piana V., Aliyev, Sh.T. and etc., 2009). These, in turn, create additional ground for the innovation of the country's economy, including the intensification of the innovative development of the agricultural sector (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2014).

The agricultural sector is one of the economic sectors that is most supported and paid attention to by the state in the structure of the national economy of Azerbaijan. It is in this sector that the food security problems of our country are solved in the context of global food security, and the fate of self-sufficiency in important food products is considered here. Therefore, in recent years, the state has made strategic decisions regarding the production of agricultural products and the development of the agricultural sector, provided numerous concessions, including tax breaks. At the same time, mechanisms for subsidizing various agricultural products and agricultural products in general have been developed and implemented. The "Rules for Subsidizing the Production of

Agricultural Products” were approved by the Decree of the President of the country dated June 27, 2019 (Kənd təsərrüfatı məhsulları istehsalının subsidiyalaşdırılması Qaydası, 2019). These rules are improved and updated every year. In general, there are more than 40 types of subsidies in agriculture and the agrarian sector as a whole (Aqrar Subsidiya Şurası 2022-ci il üçün subsidiya əmsallarını açıqladı, 2022). At the same time, based on the current crisis nature of global food security, a number of measures have been envisaged to increase the level of self-sufficiency in food wheat in accordance with the Decree of the President of the country dated July 19, 2022. A new subsidy mechanism has been established with favorable terms for the cultivation and supply of wheat, an important food product (Ərzaqlıq buğda ilə özünütəminatmə səviyyəsinin yüksəldilməsinə dair bir sıra tədbirlər haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Fərmanı, 2022). On the other hand, the mechanisms for providing agricultural machinery and agricultural organic fertilizers on preferential terms are also operational. All this has created favorable conditions for the sustainable development of the agricultural sector and the active application of advanced technologies. However, it should be noted that in a period of increasing global food security, there is a need to update the goals set for the agricultural sector, and this factor also determines the more intensive development of the agricultural sector in the liberated territories. For example, as we mentioned earlier, the opportunities for growing productive varieties of food wheat, which is an important food product, in most districts of the Karabakh economic region and for processing it in these areas, and for establishing processing enterprises, are noteworthy. On the other hand, there are sufficient resources for the creation and operation of multifunctional agricultural parks and agro-industrial parks.

We would like to touch on one issue, we believe that in order to accelerate the development of the agricultural sector in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions, there is a need to create economic activity spaces with the status of free economic zones (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2008). Such economic zones have a positive impact on the expansion of export-oriented activities and the country's export structure [Агаев С.Г., Алиев Ш.Т., 2004]. In addition, similar multifunctional economic mechanisms with a package of incentives create a more favorable environment for entrepreneurship and investment activity (Алиев Ш.Т., 2012).

When formulating and implementing conceptual approaches to the development of the agricultural sector in the Karabakh economic region, it may be useful to consider the following: 1) considering the possibilities of producing a wide range of agricultural products (grains, sugar beets, grapes, cotton, corn, fodder crops, melons, fruits and vegetables, etc.), the creation of modern technology-based and competitive agro-processing enterprises should be given special attention, and 2) the organization of processing complexes for technical crops in this economic region, as a result of which the development of the textile industry and the creation of large complexes of the food industry should be considered. Specialist-researchers in agriculture and the agricultural sector in general F.F. Fikritzade and S.I. Hajiyeva gave directions for the restoration of the agricultural sector in the liberated territories: 1) planning for the efficient use of land and water resources, taking restoration measures and conducting land reform; 2) the establishment of livestock farms; 3)

creation of a supply base for agrotechnical services, seeds, fertilizers and pesticides; 4) creation of logistics infrastructure for the supply and trade of products; 5) creation of agro-processing enterprises; 6) training of agricultural specialists and organization of information and advisory services; and 7) creation of a specific state support mechanism.

Along with these, in our opinion, it is also possible to create a network of agro-processing enterprises in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions and, by productively using the potential in the region, contribute to increasing the level of self-sufficiency in our country for many agricultural products, as well as to form an export potential for agricultural products.

Conclusions

Thus, in order to implement the strategy for the reconstruction of post-conflict territories in Azerbaijan, it is necessary to organize management and use various instruments of state policy more actively, and it is important to take into account a group of factors related to this. On the other hand, we believe that in the near future, conceptual approaches to the development of the agrarian sector in the Karabakh and East-Zangezur economic regions will be further improved, and the implementation processes will enter the maximum intensive phase. In these areas, it is important to pay more attention to a group of factors:

- In establishing a reconstruction model in post-conflict territories, the national and economic interests of our country should be taken into account, and the priority of the development of the agrarian sector, which is one of the traditional sectors of the economy, should be kept in the spotlight;
- In the Karabakh and East-Zangezur economic regions, it may be more efficient to give more priority to the development of the agrarian sector in the areas of fruit growing, vegetable growing, grain growing, cotton growing, viticulture, livestock breeding, beekeeping and poultry production, etc.
- In the development of agriculture and the organization of the agrarian sector as a whole, the development of traditional forms of activity should be ensured in accordance with new challenges from a conceptual point of view, taking into account the requirements of the modern era;
- The evaluation of progressive world experience and the application of high technologies in the development of various sectors of agriculture should be given maximum priority;
- In the creation and development of the material and technical base of the agrarian sector, the goals of providing our country with important food products should be taken as the basis, and the creation of a network of competitive enterprises specialized in these areas, clusters, agro-industrial parks should be brought to the fore, etc.

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